

Diagnosis of PV module based on neural network using performance indices

Nadjib Mekhaznia, Riad Khenfer

Laboratory of Electronics and Advanced Telecommunications, Department of Electrical Engineering,
Université Mohamed El Bachir El Ibrahimi of Bordj Bou Arreridj, Bordj Bou Arreridj, Algeria

Article Info

Article history:

Received Jan 5, 2023

Revised Mar 20, 2023

Accepted Mar 31, 2023

Keywords:

Confusion matrix

Diagnosis

Neural network

Photovoltaic system

ROC curves

ABSTRACT

Solar energy is an inexhaustible and clean renewable energy. Its exploitation through photovoltaic panels is clearly increasing in the world as ecologic energy. But like the conventional power grids, this new green energy could be affected by several defects that could reduce its performance, cause negative economic and safety impacts. These faults are multiple and of different natures. their consequences are based on their dangerousness. They can cause malfunction, power reduction and even total shutdown of the PV. The goal of this contribution is to implement an artificial method based on the ANN to diagnose the faults of the solar modules and to study the interest of the performance indices for the interpretation of the results of the diagnosis of the PV module. The results obtained are widely commented by different performance indices of confusion matrix and ROC curves. The neural network-based diagnostic system has a high accuracy and training was efficient because the curves of the cases are in the vicinity of unity i.e., a perfect classification.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Nadjib Mekhaznia

Laboratory of Electronics and Advanced Telecommunications, Department of Electrical Engineering

Université Mohamed El Bachir El Ibrahimi of Bordj Bou Arreridj

Bordj Bou Arreridj, 34030, Algeria

Email: nadjib.mekhaznia@univ-bba.dz

1. INTRODUCTION

The production of electrical energy is an index of development and a vital energy need of industrialized societies which is monotonously increasing. Also, developing countries require more electrical energy to boost their development. In view of the dangerous climate change and following the policy to fight against global warming recommended by the UN, countries are asked to switch to carbon-free energies, in this case renewable energies. There are ecologic energies as the sun, biomass, and others form of energies. In this paper we are interested in the system of photovoltaic which produces electrical energy from the sun [1]–[8]. The production of electrical energy from solar energy depends on multiple factors such as climatic conditions, electrical configurations and the various faults that could take place, and other non-critical factors [9], [10]. In practice multiple factors have been detected which contribute to increase losses such as MPPT error, losses wiring, faults such as short circuit and open circuit faults, ageing of materials [11]. The detection and diagnosis of faults in PV systems are vital for the safe operation of the PV plant for the continuity of the service [12]–[18]. In this paper is to present a method using ANN [13]–[18] for diagnosing faults in the system. It is able to detect faults that occur as PV modules, bypass diodes and short-circuit. Also, the contribution gives a numerical interpretation of the results obtained by using several performance indices and a detailed analysis of the confusion matrix.

2. MODELING PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEM

Figure 1 shows the single diode model of the solar cell. Where, R_s series resistor, R_{sh} shunt resistor, and the equivalent circuit above can be written:

$$I_{ph} = I_d + I_{sh} + I \tag{1}$$

$$I_d = I_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{V+R_s I}{V_t a}\right) - 1 \right] \tag{2}$$

$$I_{sh} = \left(\frac{V+R_s I}{R_{sh}}\right) \tag{3}$$

then,

$$I = I_{ph} - I_d - I_{sh} \tag{4}$$

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{V+R_s I}{V_t a}\right) - 1 \right] - \left(\frac{V+R_s I}{R_{sh}}\right) \tag{5}$$

where I_{ph} is the photo-current, I_d is the diode current, I_{sh} is the current in shunt resistance, I_0 is the saturation current of the diode, R_s is the resistance series cell, R_{sh} is the shunt resistance cell, a is the diode quality (or ideality) factor and V_t is the thermal voltage and it can be defined by:

$$V_t = \frac{N_s K T}{q} \tag{6}$$

where, N_s is the number of cells connected in series, K is the Boltzmann constant ($1.385410^{-23} JK^{-1}$), q is the electron's charge ($e = 1.6 \cdot 10^{-19} C$), and T is the temperature of the cell [19], [20].

Figure 1. Equivalent circuit of a solar cell

– Photovoltaic module electrical characteristics

Diagnosis using neural networks has been tested on the SunPower SPR-X20-2506BLK photovoltaic module. Table 1 shows electrical characteristics. Figure 2 shows I-V and P-V characteristics of the PV module for two temperatures 25 °C and 45 °C.

Figure 2. Electrical characteristics I-V and P-V of the SunPower SPR-X20-2506BLK

Table 1. Electrical characteristics of the SunPower SPR-X20-2506BLK

Electrical characteristics	Value
Maximum power (W)	249.952
Cells per module (Ncell)	72
Open circuit voltage Voc (V)	50.93
Short circuit current Isc (A)	6.2
Voltage at maximum power point Vmp (V)	42.8
Current at maximum power point Imp (A)	5.84

3. METHODOLOGY

Diagnosis is applied to PV system based on a string of four modules [21]–[26]. The irradiation and temperature are 1000 W/m² and 25 °C. Each PV is connected to a bypass diode. The first simulation is the healthy case and the second simulation is the faulty case with two PV modules (2 and 3) short-circuited. The outputs voltage, current and power of two simulations represent the dataset of the neural network which it is used during training. It has three inputs, voltage, current, and power of the panel with 7106 samples each, ten hidden neurons and an output of two-class with 7106 samples as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Design of the neural network

4. SIMULATION AND DISCUSSION

The voltage, current and power of each simulation are saved in files. With appropriate commands, the three vectors form the inputs to the neural network. The training was carried out by the scaled conjugate gradient backpropagation method. The simulation system on Figure 4 has a string with four modules, four bypass diodes. Figure 5 shows the diagnostic model based on neural networks under Simulink. It is formed by the input, the neural network and the visualization of classes. The short circuit of two modules decreased both current and power of the PV system shown in Figures 6 and 7.

Figure 4. Simulation system

Figure 5. PV diagnostic system based on neural networks

Figure 6. Electrical characteristics I-V for healthy case and faulty

Figure 7. Electrical characteristics P-V for healthy case and faulty

Figure 8 presents the receiver operating characteristic curves which represent the sensitivity for all the possible threshold values. The sensitivity is the ability of the test to correctly detect defective cases and specificity is the ability of the test to correctly detect healthy cases. According to Figures 8 and 9, the proposed diagnostic system has a high accuracy and training was efficient because the curves of the cases are in the vicinity of unity i.e., a perfect classification.

Figure 8. Receiver operating characteristic curves

Figure 9. Performance

Figure 10, the diagonal cells indicate the number and percentage of correct classification. For example, 143 cases are correctly classified as normal. This corresponds to 2.0% of the total. Similarly, 6706 cases are correctly classified as short-circuit. This corresponds to 94.4% of the total. While, 66 short-circuit cases are wrongly classified as normal and this corresponds to 0.9% of the total. Similarly, 191 normal cases are wrongly classified as short circuit and this corresponds to 2.7% of the total. To explain and analyze the results of the confusion matrix, it is necessary to use different performance indices which are presented below:

- Positive (P): the number of real positive cases (short-circuit).

$$P = TP + FN$$

- Negative (N): the number of real positive cases (normal).

$$N = TN + FP$$

$$Total = P + N$$

- True positive (TP): indicates correctly that the short circuit is present.
- False positive (FP): indicates wrongly that the short circuit is present.
- True negative (TN): indicates correctly that the short circuit is absent.
- False negative (FN): indicates wrongly that the short circuit is absent.

$$TP=6706 \text{ and } FP=191$$

$$TN=143 \text{ and } FN=66$$

- Incidence rate

$$\frac{TP}{Total} = \frac{6706}{7106} = 94.4\%$$

- Prevalence

$$\frac{P}{Total} = \frac{6772}{7106} = 95.3\%$$

- Specificity: the proportion of negative cases correctly predicted.

$$\frac{TN}{TN + FP} = \frac{143}{143 + 191} = 42.8\%$$

- False positive rate

$$\frac{FP}{TN + FP} = \frac{191}{143 + 191} = 57.2\%$$

- False negative rate

$$\frac{FN}{FN + TP} = \frac{143}{143 + 6706} = 1.0\%$$

- Sensitivity: the proportion of positive cases correctly predicted.

$$\frac{TP}{FN + TP} = \frac{6706}{66 + 6706} = 99.0\%$$

- Negative predictive value: the true negatives in the total of negative predictions.

$$\frac{TN}{TN + FN} = \frac{143}{143 + 66} = 68.4\%$$

- False omission rate

$$\frac{FN}{TN + FN} = \frac{66}{143 + 66} = 31.6\%$$

- False discovery rate

$$\frac{FP}{FP + TP} = \frac{191}{191 + 6706} = 2.8\%$$

- Positive predictive value (precision): the true positive in the total of positive predictions.

$$\frac{TP}{FP + TP} = \frac{6706}{191 + 6706} = 97.2\%$$

- Accuracy: the proportion of correctly classified observations.

$$\frac{TP + TN}{Total} = \frac{6706 + 143}{7106} = 96.4\%$$

- Balanced accuracy:

$$\frac{Sensitivity + Specificity}{2} = \frac{0.99 + 0.428}{2} = 70.2\%$$

- Misclassification rate

$$\frac{FN + FP}{Total} = \frac{66 + 191}{7106} = 3.6\%$$

$$F1_{score} = \frac{2 \times Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} = \frac{2 \times 0.972 \times 0.99}{0.972 + 0.99} = 98\%$$

As we can see, the performance indices are multiple and complementary. They allow us to carry out a quantitative and qualitative analysis of the diagnosis of the PV panel. To analyze the performance of our PV module diagnostic model based on neural networks, we calculated accuracy (true positives and true negatives are more important) and the F1_Score (false negatives and false positives are critical) which are respectively 96.4% and 98%.

Figure 10. Confusion matrix

5. CONCLUSION

Simulation study is carried out for the diagnosis of a PV module with two classes by neural networks. In addition to the diagnosis, we were interested in the various performance indices which are multiple, complementary and allow us to give a scientific analyze of the results. The intelligent diagnostic system classified the inputs with a high accuracy. Therefore, neural networks are a very powerful and very suitable intelligent technique for the diagnosis of photovoltaic systems.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. Nagarajan and A. J. G. David, "Self-excited asynchronous generator with PV array in detained autonomous generation systems," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 358, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v14.i1.pp358-368.
- [2] D. P. Mishra, K. K. Rout, S. Mishra, M. Nivas, R. K. P. R. Naidu, and S. R. Salkuti, "Power quality enhancement of grid-connected PV system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 369, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v14.i1.pp369-377.
- [3] M. Morey, N. Gupta, M. M. Garg, and A. Kumar, "Performance analysis of voltage sensorless based controller for two-stage grid-connected solar PV system," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 444, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v14.i1.pp444-452.
- [4] S. N. N. Ibrahim, H. Zainuddin, Y. I. A. A. Rahim, N. A. Mansor, N. Muhammad, and F. L. M. Khir, "Simulation and prediction of residential grid-connected photovoltaic system performance," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 506, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v14.i1.pp506-515.
- [5] I. G. M. N. Desnanjaya, I. K. A. G. Wiguna, and I. M. A. Nugraha, "Application of PV systems in the process of drying fish for traditional fisherman," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 4, p. 2414, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i4.pp2414-2420.
- [6] H. Zeynal, Z. Zakaria, and B. Pourveys, "An efficient MPPT based photovoltaic control model considering environmental parameters," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 4, p. 2432, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i4.pp2432-2439.
- [7] H. Attia and S. Ulusoy, "A new perturb and observe MPPT algorithm based on two steps variable voltage control," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, p. 2201, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2201-2208.
- [8] A. Balal, M. Abedi, and F. Shahabi, "Optimized generated power of a solar PV system using an intelligent tracking technique," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, p. 2580, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2580-2592.
- [9] P. Shinde and S. R. Deore, "Solar PV Fault Classification using Back Propagation Neural Network," *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 5568–5574, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.35940/ijrte.F9790.038620.
- [10] P. Ducange, M. Fazzolari, B. Lazzarini, and F. Marcelloni, "An intelligent system for detecting faults in photovoltaic fields," in

- 2011 11th International Conference on Intelligent Systems Design and Applications, Nov. 2011, pp. 1341–1346, doi: 10.1109/ISDA.2011.6121846.
- [11] L. L. Jiang and D. L. Maskell, “Automatic fault detection and diagnosis for photovoltaic systems using combined artificial neural network and analytical based methods,” in *2015 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, Jul. 2015, pp. 1–8, doi: 10.1109/IJCNN.2015.7280498.
- [12] L. Schirone, F. P. Califano, U. Moschella, and U. Rocca, “Fault finding in a 1 MW photovoltaic plant by reflectometry,” in *Proceedings of 1994 IEEE 1st World Conference on Photovoltaic Energy Conversion - WCPEC (A Joint Conference of PVSC, PVSEC and PSEC)*, vol. 1, pp. 846–849, doi: 10.1109/WCPEC.1994.520093.
- [13] A. F. M. Nor, S. Salimin, M. N. Abdullah, and M. N. Ismail, “Application of artificial neural network in sizing a stand-alone photovoltaic system: a review,” *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 342, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v11.i1.pp342-349.
- [14] H. F. Hashim, M. M. Kareem, W. K. Al-Azzawi, and A. H. Ali, “Improving the performance of photovoltaic module during partial shading using ANN,” *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, p. 2435, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2435-2442.
- [15] Y. E. A. Idrissi, K. Assalaou, L. Elmahni, and E. Aitiaz, “New improved MPPT based on artificial neural network and PI controller for photovoltaic applications,” *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 13, no. 3, p. 1791, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v13.i3.pp1791-1801.
- [16] N. F. Fadzail and S. M. Zali, “Fault detection and classification in wind turbine by using artificial neural network,” *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 3, p. 1687, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i3.pp1687-1693.
- [17] H. Attia, “High performance PV system based on artificial neural network MPPT with PI controller for direct current water pump applications,” *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 10, no. 3, p. 1329, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v10.i3.pp1329-1338.
- [18] D. P. Mishra, A. S. Nayak, T. Tripathy, S. R. Salkuti, and S. Mishra, “A novel artificial neural network for power quality improvement in AC microgrid,” *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 4, p. 2151, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i4.pp2151-2159.
- [19] J. Schumacher, U. Eicker, D. Piedrushcka, and A. Catani, “Exact analytical calculation of the one diode model parameters from PV module data sheet information,” *22nd European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference*, pp. 3212–3217, 2007, [Online]. Available: <http://www.docstoc.com/docs/75320719/EXACT-ANALYTICAL-CALCULATION-OF-THE-ONE-DIODE-MODEL-PARAMETERS>.
- [20] L. Stamenic, E. Smiley, and K. Karim, “Low light conditions modelling for building integrated photovoltaic (BIPV) systems,” *Solar Energy*, vol. 77, no. 1, pp. 37–45, 2004, doi: 10.1016/j.solener.2004.03.016.
- [21] A. E. Nieto Vallejo, F. Ruiz, and D. Patiño, “Characterization of electric faults in photovoltaic array systems,” *DYNA*, vol. 86, no. 211, pp. 54–63, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.15446/dyna.v86n211.79085.
- [22] Y.-Y. Hong and R. A. Pula, “Methods of photovoltaic fault detection and classification: a review,” *Energy Reports*, vol. 8, pp. 5898–5929, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.egyr.2022.04.043.
- [23] P. Guerriero, F. Di Napoli, G. Vallone, V. D’Alessandro, and S. Daliento, “Monitoring and diagnostics of PV plants by a wireless self-powered sensor for individual panels,” *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 286–294, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1109/JPHOTOV.2015.2484961.
- [24] M. K. Alam, F. Khan, J. Johnson, and J. Flicker, “A comprehensive review of catastrophic faults in PV arrays: types, detection, and mitigation techniques,” *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 982–997, May 2015, doi: 10.1109/JPHOTOV.2015.2397599.
- [25] Y. Zhao, R. Ball, J. Mosesian, J.-F. de Palma, and B. Lehman, “Graph-based semi-supervised learning for fault detection and classification in solar photovoltaic arrays,” *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 30, no. 5, pp. 2848–2858, May 2015, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2014.2364203.
- [26] T. G. Manjunath and A. Kusagur, “Analysis of different meta heuristics method in intelligent fault detection of multilevel inverter with photovoltaic power generation source,” *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 9, no. 3, p. 1214, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v9.i3.pp1214-1222.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Nadjib Mekhaznia is PhD student at University of Bordj Bou Arreridj, Algeria. He is preparing a doctoral thesis on the intelligent diagnosis of PV systems. He received his BS and MS degrees in Electrical Engineering from University Mohamed El Bachir El Ibrahimi of Bordj Bou Arreridj, Algeria, Algeria. He can be contacted at email: nadjib.mekhaznia@univ-bba.dz.

Riadh Khenfer is associate professor of Electrical Engineering at University Mohammed EL Bachir EL Ibrahimi, of Bordj Bou Arreridj, Algeria. Currently is a member in Laboratory of Electronics and Advanced Telecommunications (ETA). His research interest include automatization, energy harvesting, power electronics and renewable energy, FPGA applications, embedded system, He can be contacted at email: riadh.khenfer@univ-bba.dz.